

METHODS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES THAT ARE INTEGRATED

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Abstract – The topical issue today is the question of what should be a foreign language lesson in modern conditions. The goals and content of education are changing, new means and technologies of education are emerging.

Key words: foreign language, lesson, modern conditions, grammatical structure, lexical composition.

I. Introduction

The main goal of learning a foreign language is the possibility of communication. Communication in a foreign language is impossible not only without mastering its lexical composition and grammatical structure, but also an important component is the idea of the socio-cultural environment of the language being studied. Therefore, the lessons should be carried out an integrated approach to learning.

II. Main part

A modern lesson should include goal setting and communication orientation. Work on the development of lexical skills goes in parallel with the study and assimilation of grammatical structures. New vocabulary is practiced in training grammar exercises. For example, the topic "Disaster" is practiced on the grammatical topic "Passive Voice": Many forests (to destroy) because of fire.

Live English speech should sound at the lesson. The use of listening exercises is a very important aspect. When doing this exercise, students are faced with a number of challenges:

- primary understanding of the text (depends on the level of knowledge of lexical and grammatical units of the language);
- adapt their hearing to foreign speech;
- supplement the text (dialogue) with missing information;
- reproduce the content;
- express their position on a given problem;
- get acquainted with the social and cultural aspects of the life of the country of the studied language.

Therefore, no doubt, an integrated approach is so important. Students, as a rule, have a lot of questions about the culture and life of the country, and if you answer them, carry out appropriate types of work, interest them, then motivation will increase and training will be crowned with success.

Over the past decades, a wide variety of “methods”, “approaches” and “techniques” in teaching foreign languages have been offered abroad: “full understanding and physical response” by Jemz Asher, “natural” approach by Krashen and Terrell, “collective language learning with the help of consultant Charles Curran, the “communicative approach” by C. Brumfit, J. Keith, W. Littlewood, H. Widdowson, “The Way of Silence” by Caleb Cataño and many others.

However, none of them has received more or less widespread distribution and recognition. Abroad, schools are dominated by the so-called “communicative” approach in a variety of ways, determined by the corresponding textbooks. In Russia, the officially recognized approach is “cognitive-communicative”, or “competence-based”. But in practice, the goal of teaching communication in a foreign language for the vast majority of graduates of schools and non-linguistic faculties remains unattainable due to the lack of a truly scientific method and textbooks of precisely this, communicative, orientation. The scientific method of teaching should be based on a scientific concept defined by a system of interrelated and interdependent principles implemented by a strategic learning model and its technological base and teaching materials.

An example of such an approach is the methods of G.K. Lozanova and G.A. Kitaygorodskaya. Their common conceptual core is a psychological orientation: the use in the educational process not only of explanation with subsequent training of the explained language material, but also of suggestion in the process of mastering language material and the formation of speech communication skills.

This concept has received a convincing scientific substantiation by the achievements of physiological science in recent decades. In 1968, Roger Sperry put forward and proved the “split brain theory”, for which he received the Nobel Prize in 1981. According to this theory, the human brain has two hemispheres with different functions. The left hemisphere specializes in logical stereotypical operations and includes the language center that performs system-structural mental operations, while the right hemisphere is responsible for emotional

manifestations. The distribution of brain functions between the hemispheres is presented in the following table.

III. Conclusion

The outwardly passive, relaxed state of students sitting in comfortable chairs in low light contributes to the active mental activity of the brain in the non-dominant right hemisphere, where it is assimilated with the greatest efficiency. The material put into memory in this way is further activated in educational activities in the classroom in personality-oriented communicative exercises to the level of stable speech skills. In the same communicative exercises, both grammar and phonetics are activated at the same time, often in game or competitive forms

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